

JEWES OF ZARAFSHAN OASIS

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Annotation

This article covers issues such as the life of the Jews who lived in the Zarafshan oasis at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, their daily lifestyle, culture and relations with the local population. The role of Jews in society and their participation in inter-ethnic processes are studied.

Key words: Jew, polyethnos, Jugut, "Jugut Guzar", "Jews of Bukhara", Hebrew, synagogue

Zarafshan oasis has long been studied as a polyethnic area. The research conducted by the researchers recorded the existing myths about the origin and lifestyle of these peoples, revealed the features of their social organization, as well as spiritual and material features. It is known that at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Jews settled in different regions of the world, including one of the central regions of Central Asia - the Zarafshan Valley. Although the number of Jews was not large, their participation in the economic life of the oasis was significant. From this point of view, it is important to take into account information related to the life and economy of the inhabitants of the region when describing the Jews and their life. In 1868, the population of only Samarkand department of Zarafshan district (excluding mountainous districts) was 179,522 people.

About the Jews, V.V. Radlov informs that "100-150 years ago they moved from Iran first to Bukhara and then to Samarkand". According to A.F. Fayziyev, based on the documents stored in the archive, the Jews lived in a separate area. According to D. L. Ivanov, the Jews living in Samarkand were in a state of lawlessness during the Muslim Emirate, and they did not have the right to build a synagogue for themselves in the city, ride horses, wear Muslim clothes, wear boots, and freely choose their place of residence. A separate area was set aside for them behind the bazaar, and all Jews lived in that area. This is how "jugut guzar" was formed. With the occupation of Samarkand by Russian troops and the establishment of Russian power, the local population and the Jews also acquired the same status of dependent population for the empire, and the same attitude was established towards them. The prohibitions against Jews introduced during the Emirate period have been abolished. As a result, the Jews began to respect the Russians and the empire's authority in the country. The

Jews became closer to the Russians and quickly began to learn the Russian language. Describing the Jews, D. L. Ivanov said that they were "the most resourceful among the local population, their merchants were competitors to all other merchants, they were the first to embrace innovation, Jews were the first to turn to Russian midwives, Russian states that they started studying in lim institutions. In addition, the Jews quickly realized all the political processes taking place in the neighboring khanates and warned the Russians about it."

With the conquest of Samarand by the Russian Empire in 1868, the legal inequalities between Central Asian Jews and the local population were somewhat alleviated. Ashkenazi Jews began to settle in the city, and their influx increased with the construction and operation of the Turkestan railway. In 1885-1890, a large synagogue was built in the center of the Jewish quarter of Samarkand. At the beginning of the 20th century, there were more than 30 synagogues in the city. In Samarkand, there is a regional community of Hasidism, the number of its members reached 853 people in 1914.

At the end of the 19th century, the term "Jews of Bukhara" appeared in official documents. Jews living in the territory of the Bukhara Emirate were called this, and Jews living in the territory of Turkestan were called "local Jews". After the events of October 1917 and the subsequent political changes in Central Asia, the term "Jews of Bukhara" began to be applied to all Jews living in the region.

A Jewish cultural center and a Hebrew-language secondary school will be established in Samarkand. In 1926, the number of Jews in Samarkand reached 7740 people, and in 1935 - 9832 people. The Samarkand Jewish community remained the largest community of Bukhara Jews. Also, the number of Ashkenazi Jews living in Samarkand reached several hundred. A Bukhara-Yiddish language secondary school also operated.

The Jewish Museum was established on the initiative of I. S. Lurie. There was also a theater in Bukhara Yiddish. One of the traditional professions of Central Asian Jews was dyeing. There were also many merchants. Merchants from Samarkand took an active part in trade with neighboring countries. Among them, we can include such families as Abramovs, Fuzaylovs, Isakharovs. At the same time, Central Asian Jews entered the agricultural sector. In the 1920s, agricultural cooperatives were established. In 1937, there were 15 Jewish kohlozs across Uzbekistan, the largest of which was in Samarkand district. In addition, there were jewelers, barbers, barbers, and doctors among the Jews; famous musicians and dancers. Throughout the Emirate of Bukhara,

professional Jewish singers - sozandas - made a name for themselves with their art.

At the beginning of the 20th century, a number of singers and musicians, who have long remained in the memory of the people of Samarkand, grew up. One of the most famous singers of the end of the 19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century was Levi Babakhanov. Murdakhay Tanburi, Kamal Hafiz, Qori Siroj, Mikhoel and Isroel Tolmasov, Mullokandov brothers can also be included in this list. Many writers and poets who wrote in the Bukhara-Jewish language worked in Samarkand.

In conclusion, it can be said that the Jews had a significant impact on the life of the population living in the Zarafshan oasis. At the end of the 19th century - in the 20th century, Jews took an active part in the inter-ethnic processes that took place in the oasis.

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